

A Study on the Impact of Digitalisation on Indian Music

Dr. K. Ashwini

Associate Professor & Co-ordinator, Department of Post Graduate Studies
Jain College, Bangalore

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S. Satish Gowtham & N. Chethan Kumar

Student- Jain College, Vasavi Temple Road, V.V Puram, Bengaluru

Abstract

The main objective of this paper is to analyse the Indian music and its history and how it evolved over a period of time. In today's world the Indian music has got a new dimension through digitalisation and it has benefited many musicians in various fields. This paper concentrates on the applications (apps) which have been introduced for the benefits of the people in/of Indian music. The paper studies the impact of or the increase of various applications in the era of digitalisation instead of physical performance which has reduced the natural music.

Keywords:- Digitalization, Music apps, Technology.

Introduction

When speaking about the music, India and Indian music plays an important role in music world. Indian music ranges from classical music to filmi music. It is the music which is very ancient and a sophisticated form. According to text, the Indian music has derived its origin from SAMAVEDA, which was be in the form of hymns, following with tonal variation which led to a origin of Indian music. Many ancient musicians like Purandaradasa, Thyagaraja, Kanakadasa, Tansen and many of them contributed towards Indian ancient music, and with this the younger generation are taking an inspiration and adapting the concept of digitalisation and taking the Indian music to a greater heights.

Indian music concentrates or gathers all type of members in the society. Indian music mainly based on the way of expression, particular musician's .Our music has a great history of many centuries. Music system of India was influenced in many kingdoms in India. Kings of ancient times are very much keen about the music and encouraged many musicians. The performance has to be done on the temple and public gatherings. The Indian kings give respects the artists and gives great level of recognition to the artists. The artists has many royal treats to the musicians. Music forms a main part of theatre. It was having great level of accessibility to all sections of the society. There was great history of theatre music also in India. Indian music has great tradition and carried great legacy and on time passed

India experienced the flavour of Bollywood with taste of both the classical and western aspects of music. Many movies are now being opposing at the Western society, movies with reduced form of music. This is spoiling India’s musical background.

Indian music is a mixture of many different types of music. Five hundred years ago, India was ruled Muslims, when it had been influenced by local territories such as the recent Nepal, Pakistan, Bangladesh. Classical music is a very important feature in most Indian audience’s lives. It gives the pleasure to the listeners. The term “Indian Classical Music” refers to two different, but related, old traditions. Both of them are very famous and come from two different parts in India. They are: the North Indian classical music tradition called Hindustani, while the South Indian expression is called Carnatic.

Indian Music is Different from Western Music in two Major Ways

1. All the Indian classical music is melodious, and
2. Indian music is never written down, and cannot be played off a written score.

If it was played off the score, it would lose its authenticity. Over centuries, the artists learn to play or sing by listening to the song. As the artist learns the song and plays it, he adds his own authenticity to the song. In this way, the work of numerous generations has been put together to make a singular song that has been made seamless over the years. This is how Indian music has survived over the years.

Hindustani classical music is based upon the 12 note scale. Carnatic classical music is based on the saptaswara. The following chart shows the comparison of the Classical notes and the Western notes:

Carnatic	Western	Just Ratios	Cents
<i>Sa</i>	P1	1 / 1	0.0000
<i>Ri₁</i>	m2	16 / 15	111.73
<i>Ri₂ or Ga₁</i>	M2	9 / 8	203.91
<i>Ga₂ or Ri₃</i>	m3	6 / 5	315.64
<i>Ga₃</i>	M3	5 / 4	386.31
<i>Ma₁</i>	P4	4 / 3	498.04
<i>Ma₂</i>	+4	17 / 12	603.00
<i>Pa</i>	P5	3 / 2	701.96
<i>Da₁</i>	m6	8 / 5	813.69
<i>Da₂ or Ni₁</i>	M6	5 / 3	884.36
<i>Ni₂ or Da₃</i>	m7	9 / 5	1017.6
<i>Ni₃</i>	M7	15 / 8	1088.3

Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Indian_classical_music

Conceptual Background

During the invasion of the mughal empire in India, the approach towards the Indian music has changed a lot. Indian classical music incorporates the legendary forms like dhrupad, khayal, tarana, khayalnuma, chaturang, dadra, tappa or thumri. The list is endless, because the styles, dictions, modes, renditions or revival of musical fashion, perhaps develops in every decade.

The Hindustani music also had a lot of praise among the kings and other forms of music like SUFI, GHAZAL, etc., became famous among the musicians. They also had the pride of performing in front of many kings. The music has evolved by the basic criteria like creativity and innovation of great music.

As a Sanskrit Shloka Says

“SHRUTHI MATHA LAYA PITHA”, and “RANJAKO JANA CHITTANAM SA RAGAHA”, 1 which means shruthi the basic tone is like mother and laya the tempo or the rhythm. In earlier days the music is to attain the salvation or mukthi.

Sources : RIGVEDA

Comparison between Traditional and Modern Music

a. Traditional Music

From the inspiration of classical music the folk form of music got birth. Then day by day the folk music were famous and folk music plays a very big role in Indian music and the traditional form of music from the ancient period of Indian music field. Many musicians gave a big contribution towards traditional pattern of music. These traditional music is famous for its devotion and spiritual part of it. These kind of music is an oldest form and also a systematic form of music. The Traditional music helps us to know represents our culture and heritage of our nation. It mainly based on the shastras and sampradaya of the Indian classical music. It has more technical aspects of music than the modern music of today generation. Tradition music has more depth and essence of Indian culture.

b. Modern Music

In modern music is totally different from the traditional music. In this modern generation the different style of music enjoyed by the younger generation and also the modern music will place an important role in the Indian society as well as in the global perception. The style of western is totally of the theme based music like nature, art, etc. the instruments used in modern music field are drums, guitars, keyboard, rhythm pads, I pads, etc. The aspects of modern music so related our music pattern where the base of the music will be same global where it only change in the perception of an artists' according to their culture of geographical area of the particular area.

Importance of Music

1. Music is very much important to human life.
2. Improves mood.
3. Reduces stress.
4. Lessens anxiety.
5. Improves memory.
6. Provides peaceful mind.
7. Improves Mental stability.
8. Improves cognition.
9. Positive vibration.
10. Improves concentration.

Digitalization in the field of Music

Digitization has made the cost of production and distribution of music recorded cheaper compare to tradition means. Internet plays an important role in marketing and promotion of music. The ability to download songs diminished the need to purchase the classical music product which consists of full length album. Browsing based on artist devotional, regional music, etc. has been accessible to the interested listeners with help smart phone. With the help of social media, independent artists are getting benefited more than the earlier days. Digitization has the biggest impact in the field of the Indian music world or the field. The entrance of digitization concept to the world has created many media to create the market in the field of music world.

Following are some of the compelling reasons for initiating digitization of music for not only archival but dissemination purposes

- Easy availability of digitization machines of high resolution at market at affordable costs for audio data.
- Easy availability and affordability of mass storage digital media.
- Availability of a host of soft wares viz. SONY Sound Forge, Cakewalk, Vinyl Studio, etc.
- Unavailability of analog machines especially the playback and duplicating machines for audio visual media.
- Unfamiliarity with analog techniques.
- Huge maintenance issues of the analog machines.

Advantages of Digitalization

Amongst several advantages of digitization, some of the most noteworthy are :

- Space required for storage of material is saved
- Easy and faster access to any type of material
- Barriers of space and time in accessing the information are overcome
- Creation of multiple copies has become easier
- Preservation for posterity is facilitated

Objectives of the Study

1. To learn the impact of digitalisation in music.
2. To understand the teaching or learning process of music through digitalisation.
3. To learn the various apps used in the digital world of music.

Statement of Problem

In the music field, there are so many problems which have arisen because of the new changes in the field of music. The music world does not escape plagiarism, copy rights, patents act etc. Therefore, a paper has been undertaken to study the impact of digitalization in the field of music.

Methods Used

Tool: Interview Schedule

Opinion of Few Musicians

1. Digitalisation is a great boon to the musicians and music world which has made more easy to access and learn.
2. Digitalisation builds or integrates the music to next level and it is helpful to globalise the Indian music.
3. Digitalisation is also having a limitations like track recordings of music, karaoke has taken away the opportunities of many instrumental musicians.
4. Too much of digitalisations lead to the taste of artificial music or the electronic form of music.

Applications Introduced after Digitalisation

1. Gaana
2. Saavn
3. Hungama
4. Wynk music
5. Jio music

6. Spotify
7. Sound cloud
8. Tanpura Droid
9. Lehra studio
10. Google play music

Global Streaming Music Subscription Market H1 2018

The above graph indicating the music streaming application’s subscription.

1. By analysing this graph the usage of digitalised application has been increased and the revenue collected through music subscription market in 2018, is \$3,498.
2. By analysing the above pie chart spotify application tops the chart by having a 36% space in the music subscription market.
3. Application space in the music subscription market graph (as in %)
 - a) Spotify – 36%
 - b) Apple music – 19%
 - c) Amazon- 12%
 - d) Tencent music-8%
 - e) Deezer-3%
 - f) Google-3%
 - g) Pandora -3%
 - h) MelON-2%
 - i) Others-14%

Graph of Different Criteria of digitalisation in music (2007 & 2017)

Criteria	2007	2017
Physical	14.2	5.2
Digital (Exclusive of Streaming)	2.7	2.8
Streaming	0.2	6.6
Performance rights	1.2	2.4
Synchronisation	0	0.3

Sources: IFPI.

Analysis

- In the year of 2004 the revenue earned was \$0.4 billion.
- In the year of 2005 the revenue earned was \$1.2 billion.
- In the year of 2006 the revenue earned was \$2.2 billion.
- In the year of 2007 the revenue earned was \$2.9 billion.
- In the year of 2008 the revenue earned was \$4.0 billion.
- In the year of 2009 the revenue earned was \$4.4 billion.
- In the year of 2010 the revenue earned was \$4.6 billion.
- In the year of 2011 the revenue earned was \$5.1 billion.
- In the year of 2012 the revenue earned was \$5.6 billion.
- In the year of 2013 the revenue earned was \$5.9 billion.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from the study that, digitalisation has a great and good impact in the field of Indian music. It has elevated the Indian music to a global level and created a good reputation for Indian musicians, with the help of digitalisation, globally. Though, digitalisation of Indian music also has its own drawback like artificiality of music and the natural way of music has been obstructed due to the idea of digitalisation, but in spite of its drawbacks, the Indian music with the help of digitalization is making a great impact globally and the musicians can compete on a global platform with ease and confidence. Many more advantages are yet to come in the music world with the advent of digitalization.

References

1. <https://www.123helpme.com/view.asp?id=78237>
2. https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/175046/16/10_chapter%204.pdf
3. https://www.academia.edu/5370622/Case_Study_Impact_of_Digitization_on_Music_Industry_in_the_Recent_Times
4. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/276157453_The_digitization_of_music_and_the_accessibility_of_the_artist
5. https://www.google.com/search?q=digitization+of+indian+music+graph+and+charts&rlz=1C1CHBF_enIN809IN809&source=lnms&tbm=isch&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwiYm_v5m
6. <https://traditionalmusicalinstruments.wordpress.com/2011/07/14/traditional-music-and-modern-music/>